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Open Defecation and Public Health: A Case Study of Riverine Areas of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research aims to unravel the toll of open defecation on the public health of some selected countries, with a focus on Nigeria's riverine areas in Akwa Ibom State. The theory adopted in the study was the social cognitive theory. The theory addresses both the underlying determinants of health behaviour and the methods of promoting change based on interactions between individuals and the environment. A historical/descriptive survey design was adopted, and the methods of enquiry included the primary and secondary methods of data collection. Three objectives were set, and three research questions were also asked with their corresponding null hypotheses. A well-developed Likert-type scale was used for data collection. A total population of 2,338,553 and a sample size of approximately 400 respondents were drawn from the twelve (12) local government areas of the riverine areas of the state. The sample size was determined through the use of the Taro Yameni formula, calculated at 0.5 level of significance. The findings showed, among others, that there were implications of air and water pollution on the public health of the citizens of the affected countries. It was therefore recommended, among others, that the state government should carry out periodic fumigation across the riverine areas of the state and also engage the services of the Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC) in monitoring the waterways in order to stem the tide of air and water pollution in order to further preserve the public health of citizens through the preservation of aquatic life in the rivers in the state.

Keywords: Open defecation practice, public health, Citizens, Riverine Areas.

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Introduction

The subject of open defecation practice and public health is apt, has a need for urgent attention, and has often dominated academic discourse in recent times. Interestingly, due to civilization, many hamlets have metamorphosed into towns and villages, while villages and towns have advanced into small and megacities, thereby supposedly leaving behind the primitive ways of life such as open defecation in and around the environments. Against this backdrop, it is rather odd and old-fashioned to see people still patronising the age-long method of easing oneself by defecating in the bushes, forests, canals, waterways, fields, and open space, just to mention but a few. Before proceeding with this study, it is necessary to reflect on and pontificate on the subjects of open defecation and public health, even though the terms will be properly defined afterwards in the course of the work.

Open defecation is the human practice of defecating outside ("in the open") rather than into a toilet. People may choose fields, bushes, forests, ditches, streets, canals, or other open spaces for defecation. They do so either because they do not have a toilet readily accessible or due to traditional cultural practices. The practice is common where sanitation infrastructure and services are not available. Even if toilets are available, behaviour-change efforts may still be needed to promote the use of toilets. 'Open defecation-free' (ODF) is a term used to describe communities that have shifted to using toilets instead of open defecation. This can happen, for example, after community-led total sanitation programmes have been implemented.

Open defecation can pollute the environment and cause health problems and diseases. High levels of open defecation are linked to high child mortality, poor nutrition, poverty, and large disparities between the rich and the poor. Ending open defecation is an indicator being used to measure progress towards Sustainable Development Goal Number 6. Extreme poverty and a lack of sanitation are statistically linked. Therefore, eliminating open defecation is thought to be an important part of the effort to eliminate poverty. As of 2019, an estimated 673 million people practiced open defecation, down from about 892 million people (12 percent of the global population) in 2016. In that year, 76 percent (678 million) of the people practicing open defecation in the world lived in just seven countries.

In ancient times, there were more open spaces and less population pressure on the land. It was believed that defecating in the open causes little harm when done in areas with low populations, forests, or camping-type situations. With development and

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urbanisation, open defecating started becoming a challenge and, thereby, an important public health issue and an issue of human dignity. With the increase in population in smaller areas, such as cities and towns, more attention was given to hygiene and health. As a result, there was an increase in global attention towards reducing the practice of open defecation. Open defecation perpetuates the vicious cycle of disease and poverty and is widely regarded as an affront to personal dignity. The countries where open defecation is most widely practiced have the highest number of deaths of children under the age of five, as well as high levels of undernutrition, high levels of poverty, and large disparities between people of means and the poor.

On the other hand, open defecation is adversely harmful to public health. The negative public health impacts of open defecation are the same as those described when there is no access to sanitation at all. Open defecation and a lack of sanitation and hygiene in general are important causes of various diseases. The most common are diarrhoea and intestinal worm infections, including typhoid, cholera, hepatitis, polio, trachoma, and others. The adverse health effects of open defecation occur because open defecation results in faecal contamination of the local environment. Open defecators are repeatedly exposed to many kinds of faecal bacteria, like Gramme-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and other faecal pathogens. This is particularly serious for young children whose immune systems and brains are not yet fully developed. Certain diseases are grouped together under the name of waterborne diseases, which are diseases transmitted via faecal pathogens in water. Open defecation can lead to water pollution when rain flushes faeces that are dispersed in the environment into surface water or unprotected wells.

Open defecation was found by the WHO in 2014 to be a leading cause of diarrheal death. In 2013, about 2,000 children under the age of five died every day from diarrhoea. Young children are particularly vulnerable to ingesting the faeces of other people that are lying around after open defecation because they crawl on the ground, walk barefoot, and put things in their mouths without washing their hands. Faeces from farm animals are equally a cause for concern when children are playing in the yard. Those countries where open defecation is most widely practiced have the highest numbers of deaths of children under the age of five, as well as high levels of malnourishment (leading to stunted growth in children), high levels of poverty, and large disparities between the rich and the poor. Open defecation badly harms the health of children and their quality of life, including psychological issues.

Statement of the Problem

Before now, open defecation was the order of the day, particularly for people living in riverine areas as well as places where there were more open spaces and less population pressure on land. It was believed that defecating in the open causes little harm when done in areas with low populations, forests, or camping-type situations. But, with development and urbanisation, open defecating started becoming a challenge and, thereby, an important public health issue and an issue of human dignity. With the increase in population in smaller areas, such as cities and towns, more attention was given to hygiene and health. As a result, there was an increase in global attention towards reducing the practice of open defecation. It is rather surprising to note that in some parts of developed countries, some people still practice open defecation; how much more in the underdeveloped and developing worlds?

To this end, apart from the government's effort to stem the tide of open defecation practices and promote the public health of citizens in public places in countries around the world, private citizens and corporate bodies have largely, both in their homes and business places, embraced the modern approach of defecation by providing water systems for the purpose. It is observable that in various public places like markets, business malls, schools, health centres, motor parks, local government premises, and so on, governments have provided latrines and toilet facilities for members of the public in order to not only preserve human dignity but to sustain a high level of public health among their citizens.

But, despite the efforts of the government or those of private citizens and corporate bodies in this direction, a very large percentage of the population still embraces and enjoys the open defecation practice in modern societies. As such, the health of citizens has been grossly jeopardized. In an attempt to determine the implications of open defecation on public health, some parameters were identified while unbundling the concept of open defecation as an independent variable in the topic. In that way, open defecation could cause air and water pollution, as well as environmental hazards. The lack of sanitation and hygiene as a result of open defecation in and around environments could lead to the most common diseases, such as diarrhoea and intestinal worm infections.

Others could include typhoid, cholera, hepatitis, polio, trachoma, and others. The adverse health effects of open defecation occur because open defecation results in faecal contamination of the local environment. Open defecators are repeatedly exposed to

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many kinds of faecal bacteria, like Gramme-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and other faecal pathogens. This is particularly serious for young children whose immune systems and brains are not yet fully developed. It would be interesting to also note that certain diseases are grouped together under the name of waterborne diseases, which are diseases transmitted via faecal pathogens in water. This research therefore aims to unravel the toll of open defecation on the public health, with a focus on Nigeria's riverine areas in Akwa Ibom State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this research is to unravel the toll of open defecation on public health, with focus on Nigeria's riverine areas of Akwa Ibom State.

Other subsidiary objectives include:

- i. To find out the implications of air and water pollutions on the public health of citizens of the affected countries;
- ii. To determine the level of environmental hazards caused by open defecation on the public health of citizens of those countries;
- iii. To evaluate the effects of lack of sanitation and hygiene on the public health status of citizens of the selected countries of the world.

Research Questions

In order to elicit cogent answers or responses from respondents, the research questions will be asked based on the three (3) subsidiary objectives of the research as follows:

- i. What are the implications of air and water pollutions on the public health of citizens of the affected countries?
- ii. Can the level of environmental hazards caused by open defecation on the public health of citizens of those countries under investigation be determined?
- iii. How would the effects of lack of sanitation and hygiene on the public health status of citizens of the selected countries of the world be evaluated?

Research Hypotheses

Based on the three (3) research questions, three (3) null hypotheses were also postulated to enable empirical testing.

- i. Ho: There tends not to be implications of air and water pollutions on the public health of citizens of the affected countries.

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- ii. Ho: The level of environmental hazards caused by open defecation on the public health of citizens of those countries under investigation may likely not be determined.
- iii. Ho: It seems the effects of lack of sanitation and hygiene on the public health status of citizens of the selected countries of the world cannot be evaluated.

Research Design/Methodology

The methodology used in this research was the Historical/Descriptive Survey design. This was to enable the researcher to gather data from a subset of the entire population of Akwa Ibom State, which in the case of this research, involves thirteen (13) Local Government Area in the state. Descriptive design involves analysis of an event through observation, case study and survey. Whereas, survey design involves the use of questionnaire for the collection of data. In other words, the methods of enquiry included the primary and secondary methods of data collection. The data collected were primarily to be analysed with the use of percentage tables and chi square, but space requirements hindered the process. But, the secondary sources of data included text books, official publications, journals and the internet.

Population of the Study

The entire population of Akwa Ibom State as at 2016 from the source below was 7,200,00.

S/No.	Local Government	Population
1	Ikot Abasi	169,200
2	Mkpat Enin	226,200
3	Eastern Obolo	76,500
4	Onna	157,200
5	Eket	220,600
6	Esit Eket	80,900
7	Ibena	95,500
8	Oron	111,300
9	Okobo	102,753
10	Udung Uko	67,700
11	Mbo	130,400
12	Urue Offong/Oruko	90,300
Total		2,338,553

[Wikipedia/Akwa Ibom State.gov.ng/about](https://www.wikipedia.org/wiki/Akwa_Ibom_State) – akwa – ibom/

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Sample/Sampling Techniques

This study used a simple random sampling technique to ensure that each element of the population had an equal probability of being chosen, and it selected approximately 400 respondents who were farmers, fishermen and women, traders, traditional rulers and residents in the riverine areas, who have vast knowledge of the situation in the areas. In this study, the sample size was determined using the Taro Yamani formula to be approximately 400.

The Taro Yamani formula is represented below as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + 2N(e)^2}$$

Where; N = Population of the Study

n = Sample Size

(e) = Level of significance. Note (e) = 0.05 (95%).

1 = Unit (a constant)

$$n = \frac{2,338,553}{1 + 2,338,553(e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{2,338,553}{1 + 2,338,554(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{2,338,553}{2,338,554(0.0025)}$$

$$n = 2,338,554 \times 0.0025 = 5,846.385$$

$$n = \frac{2,338,553}{1 + 5,847.385}$$

$$n = \frac{2,338,553}{5,847.386}$$

$$n = 399.93$$

$$\text{approx.} = 400$$

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Significance of the Study

The significance of the study is categorised into two parts, namely: theoretical and empirical significance.

i. Theoretical significance:

The research on the toll of open defecation on the public health of the citizens of some selected countries of the world will contribute immensely to the existing body of knowledge, and as such, it will serve as a reference material for future researchers both in environmental management and in public health, generally.

ii. Empirical significance:

The knowledge acquired from the study on the toll of open defecation on public health of the citizens of some selected countries of the world will enhance further advocacy on the need to exterminate the age-long practice of open defecation in human society. Therefore, the study will proffer experts solution to nip the problem on the bud. The legislature will find this material useful in making relevant legislations that will preserve both the environment as well as public health in the selected areas. The executive, at any level can use these materials as its policy framework to formulate its policies along the lines of environmental and public health.

Definition of Concepts:

i. Open Defecation Practice

Simply put, open defecation is the human practice of defecating outside ("in the open") rather than into a toilet. Its practice is the mode and methods defecating. People may choose fields, bushes, forests, ditches, streets, canals, or other open spaces for defecation.

ii. Public Health

Udoh, and Fingesi, (2022) have defined public health the condition of a person's body or mind as cared for or enhanced by healthy environment, surroundings, healthcare provisions as well as health conditions of service by government to the public or the generality of the people in society. But Turnock in Etukidem et al (2020) view public health as a collective effort to identify and address the unacceptable realities that result

in preventable and avoidable health outcomes, and it is the composite of efforts and activities that are carried out by people committed to this end.

iii. **Citizens:** Citizen refers to a person who has the legal right to belong to a particular country.

iv. **Riverine Areas of Akwa Ibom State**

According to Hornby (2008), a river is a natural flow of water that continues in a long line across land to the sea/ocean. Based on the above definition, the term, "Riverine" is the composition of the entire area that is bounded by a river. In Akwa Ibom State, for instance, there are 12 Local Government Areas that are bounded by river, and they are referred to as riverine local government areas. These include: Eastern Obolo, Eket, Esit-Eket, Ibeno, Ikot Abasi, Mbo, Mkpato-Enin, Okobo, Onna, Oron, Udung-Uko and Urue-Offong/Oruko.

v. **Local Governments Areas of Akwa Ibom State**

Akwa Ibom State consists of thirty-one (31) Local Government Areas. They include: Abak, Eastern Obolo, Eket, Esit-Eket, Essien Udim, Etim-Ekpo, Etinan, Ibeno, Ibesikpo-Asutan, Ibiono-Ibom, Ika, Ikono, Ikot Abasi, Ikot Ekpene, Ini, Itu, Mbo, Mkpato-Enin, Nsit-Atai, Nsit-Ibom, Nsit-Ubium, Obot-Akara, Okobo, Onna, Oron, Oruk Anam, Ukanafun, Udung-Uko, Uruan, Urue-Offong/Oruko and Uyo.

Theoretical Framework

The theory found to be most appropriate for a study as this, that has to do with human health is the social cognitive theory, and it is adopted here.

Social Cognitive Theory

One of the most widely used models in health promotion is social cognitive theory. It addresses both underlying determinants of health behaviours and the methods of promoting change and is based on the interactions between individuals and the environment. It focuses on the way in which an environment shapes human behaviour.

Basic components of social cognitive theory

- Reciprocal determinism
- Environmental context
- Individual
- Behaviour

Application of Social Cognitive Theory in HoMBReS

HoMBReS is a community-based program aimed at lowering the risk of HIV and other sexually transmitted illnesses among Latino men in rural areas of the United States. The program trains "Navegantes" (Navigators) who deliver knowledge and risk reduction resources to the target community, based on the Social Cognitive Theory.

Empirical Literature Review

Clasen et al. (2014) define open defecation as the human practice of defecating outside ("in the open") rather than in a toilet. People may choose fields, bushes, forests, ditches, streets, canals, or other open spaces for defecation. They do so either because they do not have a toilet readily accessible or due to traditional cultural practices. The practice is common where sanitation infrastructure and services are not available. Even if toilets are available, behaviour-change efforts may still be needed to promote the use of toilets. 'Open defecation-free' (ODF) is a term used to describe communities that have shifted to using toilets instead of open defecation. This can happen, for example, after community-led total sanitation programmes have been implemented.

According to WHO and UNICEF (2014), open defecation can pollute the environment and cause health problems and diseases. High levels of open defecation are linked to high child mortality, poor nutrition, poverty, and large disparities between the rich and the poor. Ending open defecation is an indicator being used to measure progress towards Sustainable Development Goal Number 6. Extreme poverty and a lack of sanitation are statistically linked. Therefore, eliminating open defecation is thought to be an important part of the effort to eliminate poverty (Ahmad, 2014). In their further verifications, WHO and UNICEF (2019), in corroboration with Devine (2009), opined that as of 2019, an estimated 673 million people practiced open defecation, down from about 892 million people (12 percent of the global population) in 2016. In that year, 76 percent (678 million) of the people practicing open defecation in the world lived in just seven countries, according to WHO and UNICEF (2017).

But, from the original archives in O'Reilly's (2016) custody, it is gathered that in ancient times, there were more open spaces and less population pressure on land. It was believed that defecating in the open causes little harm when done in areas with low populations, forests, or camping-type situations. With development and urbanisation, open defecation started becoming a challenge and, thereby, an important public health issue and an issue of human dignity. With the increase in population in smaller areas, such as cities and towns, more attention was given to hygiene and health. As a result, there was an increase in global attention towards reducing the practice of open defecation. WHO and UNICEF (2014) further pontificate that open defecation perpetuates the vicious cycle of disease and poverty and is widely regarded as an affront to personal dignity. The countries where open defecation is most widely practiced have the highest numbers of deaths of children under the age of five, as well as high levels of undernutrition, high levels of poverty, and large disparities between people of means and the poor.

The term "open defecation" became widely used in the water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) sector from about 2008 onwards. This was due to the publications by the Joint Monitoring Programme for Water Supply and Sanitation (JMP) and the UN International Year of Sanitation. The JMP is a joint programme by WHO and UNICEF that was earlier tasked to monitor the water and sanitation targets of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs); it is now tasked to monitor Sustainable Development Goal Number 6. For monitoring MDG Number 7, two categories were created: 1) improved sanitation; and 2) unimproved sanitation. Open defecation falls into the category of unimproved sanitation. This means that people who practice open defecation do not have access to improved sanitation. In 2013, World Toilet Day was celebrated as an official UN day for the first time. The term "open defecation" was used in high-level speeches that helped draw global attention to this issue (for example, in the "call to action" on sanitation issued by the Deputy Secretary-General of the United Nations in March 2013).

Open-Defecation-Free

Cavill et al. (2015) coinage "Open defecation-free" (ODF) is a phrase first used in community-led total sanitation (CLTS) programmes. ODF has now been used in other contexts. The original meaning of ODF stated that all community members are using sanitation facilities (such as toilets) instead of going to the open for defecation. This

definition was improved, and more criteria were added in some countries that have adopted the CLTS approach in their programmes to stop the practice of open defecation.

Reasons for Open Defecation

The reasons for open defecation are varied. It can be a voluntary, semi-voluntary, or involuntary choice. Most of the time, a lack of access to a toilet is the reason. However, in some places, even people with toilets in their houses prefer to defecate in the open (Cavill et al., 2015).

A few broad factors that result in the practice of open defecation are listed below:

1. No Toilet

- **Lack of infrastructure:** People often lack toilets in their houses, or in the areas where they live (WHO and UNICEF, 2014; Routray et al. (2015).

- **Lack of toilets in other places:** Lack of toilets in places away from people's houses, such as schools or on farms, leads to open defecation (Routray et al., 2015). Another example is a lack of public toilets in cities, whether by a reluctance among businesses to allow patrons to use their toilets or limited hours (e.g. if there are no 24-hour businesses in town and someone needs to use the toilet after regular business hours), which can be a big problem for homeless people.

- **Use of toilets for other purposes:** In some rural communities, toilets are used for other purposes, such as storing household items, animals, or farm products or use as kitchens. In such cases, people go outside to defecate (Bardosh, 2015).

2. Uncomfortable or Unsafe Toilets

- **Poor quality of toilets:** Sometimes people have access to a toilet, but the toilet might be broken, or of poor quality – outdoor toilets (pit latrines in particular) typically are devoid of any type of cleaning and reek of odours. Sometimes, toilets are not well lighted at all times, especially in areas that lack electricity. Others lack doors or may not have water. Toilets with maggots or cockroaches are also disliked by people, so they go outside to defecate (O'Connel, 2017; Kwiringira et al., 2014; Routray et al., (2015).

· **Risky and unsafe:** Some toilets are risky to access. There may be a risk to personal safety due to lack of lights at night, criminals around them, or the presence of animals such as snakes and dogs. Women and children who do not have toilets inside their houses are often faced with accessing shared or public toilets, especially at night (Kwiringira et al., 2014). Tsinda et al. (2013) has it that accessing toilets that are not located in the house might be a problem for disabled people, especially at night. In some parts of the world, Zambia for example, very young children are discouraged from using pit latrines due to the risk of them falling through the open drop-hole. In such cases when there is no other available sanitation facility, children are encouraged to practice open defecation (UNICEF, 2015).

· **Presence of toilet but not privacy:** Some toilets do not have a real door, but have a cloth hung as a door. In some communities, toilets are located in places where women are shy to access them due to the presence of men (O'Reilly, 2006; Tsinda et al., 2013; Routray et al., 2015).

· **Lack of water near toilet:** Absence of supply of water inside or next to toilets cause people to get water from a distance before using the toilet (Routray et al., 2015). This is an additional task and needs extra time.

· **Too many people using a toilet:** This is especially true in the case of shared or public toilets. If too many people want to use a toilet at the same time, then some people may go outside to defecate instead of waiting. In some cases, people might not be able to wait due to diarrhea (or the result of an Inflammatory Bowel Disease emergency).

· **Fear of the pit getting filled:** In some places, people are scared that their toilet pits will get filled very fast if all family members use them every day. So, they continue to defecate outside in order to delay the toilet pit filling up. This is especially true in the case of a pit latrine (Kwiringira et al., 2014 and Tsinda et al., 2013).

3. Unrelated to Toilet Infrastructure

· **Lack of awareness:** People in some communities do not know about the benefits of using toilets (Yadav, 2016).

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- **Lack of behaviour change:** Some communities have toilets, yet people prefer to defecate in the open (Cavill et al, 2015). In some cases, these toilets are provided by the government or other organizations and people do not like them, or do not value them. They continue to defecate in the open. Older people are often found to defecate in the open and are hesitant to change their behavior and go inside a closed toilet (Routray et al, 2015).
- **Prefer being in nature:** This happens mostly in less populated or rural areas, where people walk outside early in the morning and go to defecate in the fields or bushes. They prefer to be in nature and the fresh air, instead of defecating in a closed space (Ahmad, 2014). There may be a cultural or habitual preference for defecating "in the open air", beside a local river or stream, or in the bush.
- **Combining open defecation with other activities:** Some people wake early in the morning to go their farms. Some consider it a social activity, especially women, who like to take some time to go out of their homes. While on their way to the fields for open defecation they can talk to other women and take care of their animals (Routray et al., 2015).
- **Social norms:** Open defecation is a part of people's life and daily habits in some regions. For instance, a 2011 survey in rural East Java, Indonesia, found that many men considered the practice 'normal', and having distinct benefits such as social interaction and physical comfort. In some cultures, there may be social taboos, such as a father-in-law may not use the same toilet as a daughter-in-law in the same household (Mara, 2017).
- **Social or personal preferences:** Open defecation is a preferred practice in some parts of the world, with many respondents in a survey from 2015 stating that "open defecation was more pleasurable and desirable than latrine use" (Mara, 2017).
- In some societies, open defecation is an intentional and widely used means of fertilization.

· **Faecal incontinence:** This medical condition can result in abrupt 'emergencies' and not enough time to access a toilet.

4. Public Defecation for other Reasons

In developed countries, open defecation can be due to homelessness. Open defecation in developed areas is also considered to be a part of recreational outdoor activities such as camping in remote areas. It is difficult to estimate how many people practice open defecation in these communities.

Countries with High Numbers of People Who Openly Defecate

The practice of open defecation is strongly related to poverty and exclusion, particularly in the case of rural areas and informal urban settlements in developing countries. The Joint Monitoring Programme for Water Supply and Sanitation (JMP) of UNICEF and WHO has been collecting data regarding open defecation prevalence worldwide. The figures are segregated by rural and urban areas and by levels of poverty. This programme is tasked with monitoring progress towards the Millennium Development Goal (MDG) relating to drinking water and sanitation. As open defecation is one example of unimproved sanitation, it is being monitored by JMP for each country, and results are published on a regular basis by WHO and UNICEF (2015 and 2017). The figures on open defecation used to be lumped together with other figures on unimproved sanitation but have been collected separately since 2010.

The current estimate is that around 673 million people practice open defecation (WHO, UNICEF, 2019; Devine, 2009). The number of people practicing open defecation fell from 20 percent in 2000 to 12 percent in 2015. In 2016, the estimate was for 892 million people with no sanitation facility whatsoever and therefore practicing open defecation (in gutters, behind bushes, in open water bodies, etc.). Most people (9 of 10) who practice open defecation live in rural areas, but the vast majority live in two regions (Central Africa and South Asia). In 2016, seventy-six percent (678 million) of the 892 million people practicing open defecation in the world lived in just seven countries (WHO and UNICEF, 2017 and UNICEF, 2021).

Some countries with large numbers of people who openly defecate are listed in the table below:

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People practicing open defecation by country – in alphabetical order (use up and down arrows to order by numbers).

Country	Total population	Percentage and Number of people who defecate in the open	Other estimates (based on government-provided data or other sources)
Afghanistan	38,346,720	11-14% or 4.2 million (Chheng, 2021)	
Cambodia	16,949,415	17% or 2.8 million (Chheng, 2021)	
Chad	16,244,513	69% or 11 million (2020)	
China	1,411,778,724	1% or ~13 million (2018)	
Eritrea	5,228,000	76% or 4 million (2017)	
Ethiopia	117,876,227	18% or 20.1 million (Abebe, 2020)	
India	1,352,642,280	1.4% or 19 million	The National Annual Rural Sanitation Survey of India reported that 96.5% of rural households in India had toilets. The Indian government's own estimate in January 2019 was 1.4% or 19 million (NDTV, 2019).
Indonesia	270,203,917	9% or 25 million (Recordnepal, 2020)	
Nepal	28,095,714	10% or 2.8 million (NDTV, 2019)	
Niger	24,112,753	68% or 14 million (2017)	
Nigeria	211,400,708	24% or 48 million (UNICEF, 2021)	
Pakistan	225,199,937	7% or 15 million (World Bank, 2021)	
Philippines	106,651,394	4% or 4 million (Lalu, 2020)	

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South Sudan	12,778,250	63% or 6 million (2019)	
Sudan	44,909,353	27% or 11 million (2017)	
Somalia	17,066,000	37% or 6.3 million (Kun, 2017)	
Vietnam	96,208,984	4% or 3.7 million (Kun, 2017)	
Yemen	34,277,612	9.7% or 3.3 million	

Swachh Bharat Mission, 2014

Open defecation, according to Zakaria (2019), Dinnoo (2014), and Koffey (2017), has been an issue in India. According to a WaterAid report, India has the highest number of people without access to basic sanitation, despite government efforts under the Swachh Bharat Mission. About 522 million people practiced open defecation in India in 2014, despite having access to a toilet. Many factors contributed to this, ranging from poverty to government corruption (Zakaria, 2019; Dinnoo, 2014; and Koffey, 2017).

Since then, through Swachh Bharat, a two-phase programme managed by the Indian government, India has constructed around 100 million additional household toilets, which would benefit 500 million people in India, according to the statistics provided by the Indian government (Phase 1: 2014–2019, Phase 2: 2020–2025). A campaign to build toilets in urban and rural areas achieved a significant reduction in open defecation between 2014 and 2019. In September 2019, the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation honoured Indian leader Narendra Modi for his efforts in improving sanitation in the country.

According to UNICEF, the number of people without a toilet was reduced from 550 million to 50 million. There have also been reports of people not using the toilets despite having one, although according to the World Bank, 96% of Indians used the toilets they had (Regan and Suri, 2019; Aman, 2021). In October 2019, Modi declared India "open defecation-free," though this announcement was met with scepticism by experts who cited slowly changing behaviours, maintenance issues, and water access issues as obstacles that continued to block India's goal of being 100% open defecation-free (Kuchay, 2019). With the success of the Swachh Bharat Mission, Modi launched

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Phase 2 from 2020 to 2025. During Phase 2, the government is to focus on the segregation of waste and further eliminating open defecation.

Pakistan

In 2017, WaterAid reported that 79 million people in Pakistan lacked access to a decent toilet (Daily Times, 2021). In 2018, 10%, or 22 million people, in Pakistan practiced open defecation, according to UNICEF (The Hindu, 2021). As of 2020, 7%, or 15 million people, in Pakistan practiced open defecation, UNICEF reported (World Bank, 2027).

United States

In recent decades, a combination of factors has led to a dramatic decline in the availability of public restrooms in the United States. Once ubiquitous, pay toilets, which charged a small fee per user, fell out of favour in the 1970s and were, in most cases, not replaced by free public restrooms. Public restrooms in American cities developed a reputation for unsanitary conditions, drug use, and vandalism, leading to many cities closing or restricting access to them. The increase in homelessness nationwide has also increased the need for public toilets, but many cities have closed public toilets due to concerns that homeless people would vandalise or use drugs in them. As a result, open defecation has been increasing in American cities (Bloomberg.com, 2021).

In San Francisco, open defecation complaints for street faeces increased fivefold from 2011 to 2018, with 28,084 cases reported. This was mainly due to the rising amount of homelessness in the city (Moffit, 2019). Similar problems were reported in Los Angeles (Joel and Amy, 2020) and Miami (Robertson, 2019). The Mad Pooper was the name given to an unidentified woman who regularly defecated in public places while jogging during summer 2017 in the U.S. city of Colorado Springs (Runner's World, 2017).

Public Health

The negative public health impacts of open defecation are the same as those described when there is no access to sanitation at all. Open defecation, along with a general lack of sanitation and hygiene, is a major cause of a variety of diseases. The most common are diarrhoea and intestinal worm infections, including typhoid, cholera, hepatitis, polio,

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trachoma, and others (United Nations, 2001; Spear et al., 2013). The adverse health effects of open defecation occur because open defecation results in faecal contamination of the local environment. Open defecators are repeatedly exposed to many kinds of faecal bacteria, like Gramme-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* and other faecal pathogens. This is particularly serious for young children whose immune systems and brains are not yet fully developed (Mara, 2017).

Certain diseases are grouped together under the name of waterborne diseases, which are diseases transmitted via faecal pathogens in water. Open defecation can lead to water pollution when rain flushes faeces that are dispersed in the environment into surface water or unprotected wells. Open defecation was found by the WHO in 2014 to be a leading cause of diarrheal death. In 2013, about 2,000 children under the age of five died every day from diarrhoea (WHO, 2013).

Young children are particularly vulnerable to ingesting the faeces of other people that are lying around after open defecation because they crawl on the ground, walk barefoot, and put things in their mouths without washing their hands. Faeces from farm animals are equally a cause for concern when children are playing in the yard. Those countries where open defecation is most widely practiced have the highest numbers of deaths of children under the age of five, as well as high levels of malnourishment (leading to stunted growth in children), high levels of poverty, and large disparities between rich and poor (WHO and UNICEF, 2014).

Research from India has shown that detrimental health impacts (particularly for early life health) are even more significant from open defecation when the population density is high: "The same amount of open defecation is twice as bad in a place with a high population density average like India versus a low population density average like sub-Saharan Africa" (Vyas, 2014). Open defecation badly harms the health of children and their life quality, including psychological issues (UNICEF, 2021).

Safety of Women

There are strong gender impacts connected with a lack of adequate sanitation. In addition to the universal problems associated with open defecation, having to urinate in the open can also be problematic for females. The lack of safe, private toilets makes women and girls vulnerable to violence and is an impediment to girls' education (House et al., 2014). Women are at risk of sexual molestation and rape as they search for places

to urinate or defecate that are secluded and private, often during hours of darkness (Lemon, 2011; House et al., 2014).

Lack of privacy has an especially large effect on the safety and sense of dignity of women and girls in developing countries. Facing the shame of having to urinate or defecate in public, they often wait until nightfall to relieve themselves. They risk being attacked after dark, meaning painfully holding their bladder and bowels all day (Cavil, 2015; Lemon, 2011). Women in developing countries increasingly express fear of assault or rape when having to leave the house after dark. Reports of attacks or harassment near or in toilet facilities, as well as near or in areas where women urinate or defecate openly, are common (Cavil, 2015; Lemon, 2011).

Prevention of Open Defecation

Strategies that can enable communities, both rural and peri-urban, to become completely open defecation-free and remain so include sanitation marketing, behaviour change communication, and 'enhanced' community-led total sanitation ('CLTS + '), supplemented by "nudging" (Mara, 2017). Several drivers are used to eradicate open defecation, one of which is behaviour change. SaniFOAM (Focus on Opportunity, Ability, and Motivation) is a conceptual framework that was developed specifically to address issues of sanitation and hygiene. Using focus, opportunity, ability, and motivation as categories of determinants, the SaniFOAM model identifies barriers to latrine adoption while simultaneously serving as a tool for designing, monitoring, and evaluating sanitation interventions (Devine, 2009; Devine, 2010). The following are some of the key drivers used to fight against open defecation in addition to behaviour change (Ahmad, 2014).

- Political will
- Sanitation solutions that offer a better value than open defecation
- Stronger public sector local service delivery systems
- Creation of the right incentive structures

Integrated Initiatives

UNICEF (2017) has opined that efforts to reduce open defecation are more or less the same as those to achieve the MDG target on access to sanitation. A key aspect is awareness-raising (for example, via the UN World Toilet Day at a global level),

behaviour change campaigns, and increasing political will and demand for sanitation. Community-Led Total Sanitation (CLTS) campaigns have placed a particular focus on ending open defecation by "triggering" the communities themselves into action.

Simple Sanitation Technology Options

Simple sanitation technology options are available to reduce open defecation prevalence if the behaviour is due to not having toilets in the household and shared toilets being too far or too dangerous to reach, e.g., at night.

1. Toilet bags

People might already use plastic bags (also called flying toilets) at night to contain their feces. However, a more advanced solution to the plastic toilet bag has been provided by the Swedish company People, which produces the "Peepoo bag," a "personal, single-use, self-sanitising, fully biodegradable toilet that prevents faeces from contaminating the immediate area as well as the surrounding ecosystem" (Wheaton, 2009). This bag is being used in humanitarian responses, schools, and urban slums in developing countries (Owako, 2012; Naeem et al., 2011).

2. Bucket Toilets and Urine Diversion

Mijthab et al. (2013) suggest that bucket toilets are a simple portable toilet option. They can be upgraded in various ways, one of them being urine diversion, which can make them similar to urine-diverting dry toilets. Urine diversion can significantly reduce odours from dry toilets. Examples of using this type of toilet to reduce open defecation are the "MoSan" toilet (used in Kenya) or the urine-diverting dry toilet promoted by SOIL (Russel, 2013) in Haiti.

Summary

The researcher's discomfort, displeasure, and dissatisfaction with the age-long practice of open defecation across the globe informed this study, but with a focus on the great negative impact it has on both the environment and the public health of the citizens of Nigeria and Akwa Ibom State in particular.

The historical/descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study. A sample of 400 respondents was selected from a population of 2,338,553 indigenes and occupants of the 12 local government areas that make up the entire riverine area of Akwa

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Ibom State using a confidence interval of 5 and a confidence level of 95% (0.05). A well-developed Likert-type scale was used in the personally structured questionnaire for data collection.

The hypotheses were tested using empirical analysis from the works of previous authors. The findings were as follows:

There were implications of air and water pollutions on the public health of the citizens of the affected countries; the level of environmental hazards caused by open defecation on the public health of citizens of those countries under investigation could be determined; and, of course, the effects of a lack of sanitation and hygiene on the public health status of citizens of the selected countries of the world could be evaluated.

Conclusion

The study on open defecation practice and its toll on the public health of citizens of some selected countries in the world, with a focus on Nigeria's riverine areas of Akwa Ibom State as a contemporary issue, was conducted at the most appropriate time. The materials gathered in this study have unravelled the immediate and remote causes of open defecation in both developed and less developed countries around the world. Although the focus of the research is on the riverine areas of Akwa Ibom State in Nigeria, a cross-cultural analysis of the concept has been tabulated to show the percentage and how several countries in the world are still embarking on or practicing open defecation.

However, Nigeria tops the chart, with 48 million people still practicing open defecation, perhaps one of the reasons for the choice of this topic. It is rather paradoxical for a developed country like China to still have those practicing open defecation, to the tune of 11 million. That being the case, other African and Asian countries that may have lesser percentages may tend to feel justified in still practicing open defecation in their various countries. Based on the study area of the research, the 12 local government areas located in the riverine coastal areas of Akwa Ibom State were studied. These include: Eastern Obolo, Eket, Esit-Eket, Ibeno, Ikot Abasi, Mbo, Mkpat-Enin, Okobo, Onna, Oron, Udung-Uko, and Urue-Offong/Oruko.

The findings of the research have served as an eye-opener and have provided adequate indices for appropriate recommendations to be made towards bringing to an end this archaic, age-long, and unfashionable cultural lifestyle around the globe. The

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three findings included that: i. There were implications of air and water pollutions on the public health of the citizens of the affected countries; ii. The level of environmental hazards caused by open defecation on the public health of citizens of those countries under investigation could be determined. iii. The effects of a lack of sanitation and hygiene on the public health status of citizens of the selected countries in the world could be evaluated.

Recommendations

Based on the three (3) findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. The State Government should carry out periodic fumigation across the riverine areas of the state and also engage the services of the Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC) in the monitoring of the waterways in order to stem the tide of air and water pollution and further preserve the public health of citizens through the preservation of aquatic life in the rivers in the state.
- ii. The private individuals, corporate bodies, and government at all levels should fight to determine and reduce the level of environmental hazards caused by open defecation on the public health of citizens of Nigeria, and Akwa Ibom State in particular.
- iii. The state ministry of health should take statistics on sanitation and hygiene-related cases and treat them the same since the effects of a lack of sanitation and hygiene on the public health status of citizens of the selected countries in the world could be evaluated. This way, there will be a drastic reduction or total extermination of such cases in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

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